

Trends and Thematic Evolution in Frontal QRS-T Angle Research: A Bibliometric Analysis
from 2020 to 2025

Original Article

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ABSTRACT

Aim: The frontal QRS-T angle (fQRST) has gained increasing attention as a simple, widely accessible electrocardiographic marker reflecting ventricular depolarization-repolarization heterogeneity and electrical instability. Beyond cardiac disorders, emerging evidence links fQRST to systemic inflammation, metabolic stress, and a variety of acute clinical conditions. Despite this growing interest, the global evolution, conceptual structure, and research dynamics of fQRST studies have not been systematically characterized.

Methodology: A bibliometric analysis was performed using the Web of Science Core Collection to identify original research articles on fQRST published between 2020 and 2025. After data cleaning and standardization, 138 eligible articles were analyzed. Performance indicators -including publication trends, country and institution productivity, journal distribution, and citation metrics- were evaluated using Bibliometrix (R). Keyword co-occurrence patterns and country-level collaboration structures were visualized through VOSviewer.

Results: Research output on fQRST increased substantially during the study period, peaking in 2023. Türkiye contributed the majority of publications (79.7%), followed by China, Italy, and Japan. The most influential articles primarily focused on coronary syndromes, repolarization abnormalities, COVID-19, arrhythmia risk, and the prognostic implications of ventricular electrical heterogeneity. Seventy-one journals published fQRST-related studies, with the Journal of Electrocardiology serving as the leading outlet. Keyword evolution demonstrated a clear thematic shift from early electrophysiological and measurement-oriented terms toward clinically oriented concepts such as mortality, heart failure, arrhythmia, and systemic inflammation. Collaboration patterns were predominantly national, indicating limited international research integration.

Conclusion: Scientific interest in the frontal QRS-T angle has expanded markedly in recent years, accompanied by thematic diversification and increasing clinical relevance. The concentration of research productivity within specific regions and the limited extent of global collaboration underscore the need for broader, multicenter efforts. Overall, the findings highlight the growing importance of fQRST as an accessible biomarker and support future research incorporating large-scale datasets and advanced analytical methods.

Keywords: Frontal QRS–T angle; Electrocardiography; Repolarization; Bibliometric analysis; Citation analysis

Introduction

Electrocardiography (ECG) remains a cornerstone diagnostic tool in both acute and chronic care settings, offering a rapid, noninvasive, and widely accessible means of assessing cardiac electrical activity [1]. Beyond conventional ECG intervals and waveforms, growing attention has shifted toward advanced electrophysiological markers that more sensitively capture myocardial heterogeneity and electrical instability. Among these markers, the frontal QRS-T angle (fQRST) represents a distinctive metric quantifying the directional discordance between ventricular depolarization and repolarization vectors [2]. Numerous studies have demonstrated that widening of this angle is associated with arrhythmic events, sudden cardiac death, and a variety of adverse clinical outcomes [3-6].

A major advantage of ECG-derived parameters is their low cost, ease of acquisition, and immediate interpretability. The fQRST angle can be obtained automatically from a standard 12-lead ECG without additional calculations, specialized software, or advanced expertise. Existing literature indicates that this parameter is not limited to isolated cardiac disorders; rather, it may act as a dynamic marker of systemic inflammatory activity. Elevated fQRST values have been reported in conditions such as sepsis, crush injury, and acute pancreatitis, reflecting diffuse myocardial stress [7-9]. Similarly, increased repolarization heterogeneity has been linked to worse outcomes in COVID-19 and in ischemic cerebrovascular events, underscoring the broader prognostic

relevance of this metric across diverse clinical contexts [10, 11].

Taken together, these observations suggest that the fQRST angle may serve as a versatile indicator applicable to a wide spectrum of pathophysiological states. Despite the expanding clinical research on this parameter, a comprehensive assessment of the scientific landscape -including publication patterns, thematic evolution, collaborative networks, and global research productivity- has not yet been conducted. According to our Web of Science (WoS) search, 254 studies were published between 2000 and 2025, and notably, 138 of these appeared within the past five years, illustrating a marked rise in scientific interest during this period and mirroring the broader surge in ECG-based biomarker research [12, 13].

The present study provides the first bibliometric analysis of research focused on the frontal QRS-T angle. By examining publications from 2020 to 2025, we aim to map global research output, identify leading contributors and collaborative structures, characterize keyword and thematic clusters, and outline the developmental trajectory of this emerging field.

Materials and Methods

1.1. Data source

This study presents a bibliometric analysis of the scientific output related to the frontal QRS-T angle (fQRST) for the period between 2020 and 2025. All data were retrieved from the Web of Science Core Collection (WoSCC). WoSCC was selected as the sole and reliable data source because

it provides standardized bibliographic information, including article titles, abstracts, author keywords, author identifiers, institutional affiliations, country information, journal sources, citation counts, and reference lists [14]. All records identified through the search were exported in the “Full Record and Cited References” format, after which data cleaning, deduplication, and variable standardization procedures were applied to construct the final dataset.

1.2. Search strategy

The search was conducted in WoSCC on December 4, 2025, to identify all publications related to the fQRST angle. The search query was designed to capture both the full terminology and commonly used abbreviations. The Topic Search (TS) field was queried using the expression: *TS = (“frontal QRS-T angle” OR “frontal QRST angle” OR “QRS-T angle” OR “QRST angle” OR “fQRST”)*. To evaluate current research trends, the search was limited to English-language articles published between January 1, 2020, and December 4, 2025. Only records categorized as “Article” were included, and the search covered the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-Expanded) and Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI). All retrieved records were exported in the “Full Record and Cited References” format for subsequent screening.

1.3. Eligibility criteria

For the eligibility assessment, only original research articles were considered. To ensure alignment with the focus of the study, records were included if they directly

addressed the fQRST angle, were published in English, and contained the essential bibliographic information required for bibliometric analysis. Studies outside the scope of fQRST, investigations of cardiac electrical parameters that did not involve the fQRST concept, review-type publications, and records with incomplete or inaccurate bibliographic data were excluded.

1.4. Study selection process

The initial search strategy yielded a total of 264 records in WoSCC without time restrictions. These records were screened by document type, and because the analysis focused solely on original research articles, all documents categorized as non-“Article” were excluded, reducing the dataset to 229 records. The study period was then restricted to January 1, 2020, through December 4, 2025, resulting in 143 articles that met the preliminary eligibility criteria. These records were further evaluated based on titles, abstracts, and keywords, and publications not directly related to the fQRST concept were excluded. Ultimately, 138 articles were included in the analysis, and the bibliometric evaluation was conducted using this final dataset. The selection process was carried out in accordance with the principles of the PRISMA 2020 flow framework (Figure 1) [15].

Figure 1: PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for study selection

1.5. Data Extraction and Preprocessing

For each record, core bibliographic fields such as the title, abstract, author keywords, author names, number of authors, institutional affiliations, countries, source journal, publication year, citation count, subject category, and WoS accession number were extracted. To address variability in author and institution names, name harmonization procedures were applied, and standardized naming conventions were used for institution and country fields. From the affiliations field, both the primary institution/country information and the unique list of all institutions and countries were derived. Journal impact factor and quartile classifications were assigned by matching WoS records with the corresponding Journal Citation Reports (JCR) data for the

relevant years. During this process, annual JIF, five-year JIF, and best quartile rankings were harmonized, and for records dated 2025, the most recent available quartile information from 2024 was used. Additionally, to maintain semantic consistency within the keyword field, synonymous terms were merged, multiple spelling variants were unified, and automatically generated Keywords Plus terms were refined when necessary. Following these steps, the final dataset was prepared for use in the bibliometric performance analyses and science-mapping procedures.

1.6. Bibliometric Analysis

1.6.1. Performance Analysis

The performance analysis evaluated annual publication trends, as well as the productivity of countries and institutions, the distribution of source journals, and citation indicators. Citation metrics included total citation counts and the mean number of citations per article. In addition, citation density was calculated to assess the relative influence of each publication over time; this metric was derived by dividing the total number of citations by the number of years elapsed since the article's publication.

1.6.2. Science Mapping

Science-mapping procedures focused on keyword co-occurrence patterns to identify the conceptual structure of the fQRST literature and to characterize its temporal evolution. Country-level collaboration patterns were also visualized to illustrate

geographic contributions within the research domain.

1.7. Statistical Analysis

The bibliometric analyses were conducted using the R software environment, employing the bibliometrix package and its web interface, Biblioshiny, for performance indicators and keyword-based evaluations. Country-level collaboration maps and keyword co-occurrence visualizations were generated using VOSviewer. Microsoft Excel was used for basic data organization and the creation of summary tables.

Results

A total of 138 original research articles published between 2020 and 2025 were included in the final analysis. The distribution of publication years showed that the earliest article within the study window was published in 2020, while the most recent record corresponded to 2025. The number of articles published per year ranged from 14 to 31. Across all publications, the mean number of citations was 3.07, with a median of 2 citations. When adjusted for years since publication, the mean citation density was 0.87, and the median citation density was 0.50. Authorship patterns indicated that the mean number of authors per article was 5.46, while the median number of authors was 4 (IQR: 2-6).

Annual Publication Trend

Between 2020 and 2025, research on the frontal QRS-T (fQRST) angle demonstrated a fluctuating yet progressively strengthening publication pattern. The annual number of articles rose from 16 in 2020 to a peak of 31 in 2023, followed by a temporary decline in 2024 and a subsequent rebound in 2025 (Figure 2).

Most Cited Articles

The citation analysis identified the ten most influential articles published between 2020 and 2025. Citation counts ranged from 9 to 21, with citation densities extending up to 5.0, underscoring the rapid dissemination and impact of several high-visibility publications. Most top-ranked studies originated from Turkey, highlighting the country's leading role in advancing fQRST research, while contributions from Italy and the United Kingdom reflected broader international engagement. The thematic focus of these highly cited works spanned coronary syndromes, repolarization abnormalities, hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, COVID-19, and genetic determinants of arrhythmic risk (Table 1).

Figure 2: Annual Publication Trend

Distribution by Countries and Institutions

The geographic distribution of publications based on corresponding author affiliations is presented in Table 2. Türkiye accounted for the vast majority of the output (79.7%), followed by China, Italy, and Japan. Publication volume and average citation counts showed substantial heterogeneity across countries. The institution-level analysis identified the University of Health Sciences, Harran University, and Süleyman Demirel University as the most productive centers based on first-author affiliations. Accordingly, the country-level density map in Figure 3 reflects publication intensity and illustrates the geographic concentration of research activity within the fQRST literature.

Figure 3: Density visualization

Journal and Quartile Distribution

A total of 71 journals contributed to the fQRST literature during the 2020-2025 period, with publication output concentrated in a small group of core sources. The Journal of Electrocardiology was the leading venue, accounting for 12.3% of all articles, followed by the American Journal of Emergency Medicine, European Review for Medical and Pharmacological Sciences, and Medicine, each contributing approximately 5%. Citation performance varied widely across journals, with mean citations ranging from 1.14 to 6.59 among the top sources. Three journals -American Journal of Emergency Medicine, Medicina-Lithuania, and Journal of Clinical Medicine- were categorized as Q1, representing the highest-impact outlets within this research domain. Detailed journal-level metrics are presented in Table 3.

WoS Subject Category Analysis

The classification of the included studies across Web of Science subject categories is shown in Figure 4. The majority of fQRST-related publications were indexed under Cardiac & Cardiovascular Systems (38.0%) and Medicine, General & Internal (32.2%), together representing more than two-thirds of the dataset. Smaller proportions were distributed across Pharmacology & Pharmacy (9.1%), Emergency Medicine (6.6%), and several less frequent categories, including endocrinology, psychiatry, and peripheral vascular disease.

Keyword Co-Occurrence and Temporal Distribution

Figure 5 presents the temporal distribution of author keywords using VOSviewer's overlay visualization. Keywords shown in blue represent earlier publications, while

green and yellow indicate more recent entries in the literature. Early studies predominantly featured terms related to electrocardiographic measurement and repolarization indices, including “frontal QRS-T angle,” “electrocardiography,” and “electrocardiogram.” In later years, additional terms such as “mortality,” “arrhythmia,” “heart failure,” and “ventricular repolarization” appeared with increasing frequency. Peripheral but recurrent keywords, including “COVID-19,” “electrical risk score,” “coronary artery disease,” and “pregnancy,” were also observed in the recent period. The distribution of colours reflects the chronological expansion of research topics within the fQRST literature.

Figure 4: Distribution of Publications Across WOS Categories

Figure 5: Keyword cloud and overlay network

Discussions

This bibliometric study demonstrates that the research field on the frontal QRS-T angle (fQRST) has evolved into a rapidly maturing scientific domain in recent years. The marked increase in publication volume between 2020 and 2025 directly reflects both the growing clinical interest in electrophysiological markers and the development of ECG-based risk models [2, 16-18]. At the same time, the fact that ECG is simple, inexpensive, widely available, and does not require additional resources for interpretation, together with the growing body of evidence that fQRST is associated with arrhythmia [19-21], mortality [6, 22-25], and electrical instability [26, 27], as well as with various systemic conditions as a potential predictor [7, 8, 11, 28, 29], collectively strengthens the scientific rationale underpinning the surge in publications observed over the last five years. By comprehensively mapping the literature, this study is the first to systematically delineate trends, research gaps, and thematic evolution within this field.

A total of 254 studies related to the frontal QRS-T angle and repolarization heterogeneity were published between 1983 and 2025, of which 138 were produced solely during the 2020–2025 period. The first study in the field is generally considered to be the electrophysiological analysis by Green et al. in 1983, which showed that QRS alternans in narrow QRS supraventricular tachycardias could be used to evaluate the underlying conduction

pathway and electrical heterogeneity. This work laid the conceptual foundation for using ventricular activation and repolarization dispersion -the core of fQRST today- as a diagnostic parameter [30]. Although a modest decline was observed in 2024, the overall trend remains upward. This pattern suggests that fQRST is gaining increasing importance in emergency medicine, cardiology, and intensive care practice as both an early risk stratification tool and an economical, accessible screening parameter. In particular, the growing automation of ECG acquisition, the proliferation of algorithms capable of processing high-volume data, and the integration of AI-assisted analyses into clinical workflows have become key technological drivers accelerating research on fQRST [31, 32].

Geographical distribution analysis revealed that Türkiye occupies a dominant leading position. This finding is fully consistent with the recent body of fQRST research originating from Türkiye that spans a wide range of clinical conditions. In addition to demonstrating isolated cardiac heterogeneity, ECG is used as a triage and exclusion tool in diseases such as pancreatitis [33], pulmonary embolism [34, 35] and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) [36, 37], as well as in emergency conditions that require urgent evaluation in the emergency department, including hyperkalemia [27] and carbon monoxide poisoning [38]. These diseases have direct or indirect cardiac involvement due to systemic stress. In Türkiye, ECG has become one of the routine investigations in

emergency departments. Meanwhile, the rising contribution of China in Asia and the research output from Italy and the United Kingdom in Europe indicate that fQRST is attracting growing global interest.

With respect to journal distribution, interdisciplinary publication platforms such as the Journal of Electrocardiology, American Journal of Emergency Medicine, Medicina-Lithuania, and Journal of Clinical Medicine stand out. This diversity confirms that fQRST research is not confined to cardiology alone but resonates across a broad range of clinical disciplines, including emergency medicine, internal medicine, intensive care, neurology, and psychiatry. Interestingly, in line with our findings, the absence of a significant association between journal impact factor and article citation counts suggests that ECG-based studies may attract substantial attention regardless of impact factor, likely because of their high clinical applicability [13].

keyword co-occurrence and thematic mapping analyses demonstrate a clear evolution in fQRST research. While earlier studies focused on technical and measurement-oriented concepts such as “electrocardiography,” “ventricular repolarization,” and “QRST angle,” more recent research has shifted toward clinically oriented concepts such as “mortality,” “heart failure,” “arrhythmia,” “COVID-19,” “stroke,” and “coronary artery disease.” As the clinical prognostic value of fQRST has become more apparent, the thematic focus of research has expanded beyond pure electrophysiologic measurement to encompass the broader

burden of systemic disease. It is known that systemic inflammation can lead to the recruitment of inflammatory cells, including neutrophils and macrophages [39]. These activated cells not only secrete cytokines and reactive oxygen species but also promote endotoxemia, thereby amplifying the inflammatory cascade and ultimately precipitating a cytokine storm. By compromising endothelial integrity, the cytokine storm disrupts myocardial microcirculation and, through alterations in autonomic nervous system function, triggers pathological autophagy; collectively, these processes contribute to myocardial injury and electrophysiological abnormalities [40, 41]. In this context, changes in fQRST may not only indicate direct myocardial damage but also serve as a marker of indirect involvement, helping to explain why the clinical research agenda in this field has progressed along this trajectory.

This thematic expansion is not limited to systemic inflammation. Recent studies have also emerged in psychiatric disorders whose metabolic underpinnings are not fully elucidated. It is frequently emphasized that the medications used in these conditions may serve as a warning signal in cardiac risk assessment. There are existing data on the predictive value of fQRST in conditions such as schizophrenia and major depressive disorder [42, 43]. In a study comparing a group of children with attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and healthy controls, an increased fQRST angle was shown to be associated with symptom severity; although the difference between medication users and non-users was not

statistically significant, a trend toward wider angles was observed in the medicated group [44]. It is well established that many antipsychotic drugs block hERG (IKr) channels, one of the principal ionic currents responsible for cardiac repolarization, thereby prolonging repolarization duration, increasing electrical dispersion, and consequently leading to greater separation between depolarization and repolarization vectors, which ultimately manifests as a widening of the fQRST angle [45, 46]. In an era of increasing psychotropic medication use, the current paucity of studies assessing the cardiac risk profile of these patients using parameters such as fQRST underscores the need for well-designed prospective studies to generate more robust evidence in this area.

In this study, more than half of the 10 most frequently cited articles were affiliated with institutions in Türkiye, with investigators such as Doğan–2020, Erdoğan–2020, Işık–2021, Karakayalı–2023, and Tekin–2022 standing out. A common feature of these authors is their clinically oriented approach to fQRST, as detailed in the preceding paragraphs [42, 47-50]. When the clinical focus of the most cited studies is examined, their primary themes are early risk stratification, estimation of atherosclerotic burden, arrhythmia prediction, and prognosis in inflammatory diseases.

At the institutional level, the most productive centers were identified as the University of Health Sciences, Harran University, Süleyman Demirel University, Mehmet Akif Ersoy Training and Research Hospital, and Gazi State Hospital. These institutions are characterized by both high

patient volumes and active publication output in emergency medicine and cardiology in Türkiye. A shared feature of these centers is that they operate in healthcare environments where ECG is used widely and rapidly in acute care pathways; consequently, there is a strong clinical demand for investigating easily obtainable prognostic parameters such as fQRST.

In terms of international collaboration, the network structure appears limited, with most partnerships remaining at the national level. Although Türkiye dominates the literature quantitatively, the number of international collaborations is low, which may constrain global visibility and methodological diversity. Countries such as the United Kingdom, Italy, and Japan contribute studies that incorporate more advanced methodologies and genetic analyses, supported by their stronger academic infrastructures. However, when the overall network is evaluated, global collaboration remains weak, and interdisciplinary consortia have not yet sufficiently formed. From a scientific perspective, this constitutes a major barrier to validating fQRST across diverse populations and establishing large-scale prospective databases. There is thus a clear need for larger, geographically diverse studies to address these gaps.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, the data collection process was restricted to the Web of Science database; therefore, some studies indexed in Scopus, PubMed, or regional databases may not have been

captured. Owing to the time-dependent nature of bibliometric indicators, articles published in 2024-2025 may have accrued fewer citations simply because insufficient time has elapsed, introducing a “citation lag” and a potential “Matthew effect” that could influence citation-based metrics. Additionally, limiting the analysis to original research articles resulted in the exclusion of review and methodological papers, which may also contribute meaningfully to the development of the field. Finally, variations in keyword standardization could partially affect the interpretation of thematic clusters. Despite these limitations, the study provides a comprehensive overview of the structure and developmental trajectory of the fQRST literature.

Conclusion

This bibliometric study demonstrates that research on the frontal QRS-T angle has increased markedly in recent years, expanded thematically, and gained growing clinical relevance. The findings show that fQRST is not merely an indicator of cardiac electrical heterogeneity but also holds meaningful prognostic value across a range of clinical conditions, including systemic inflammation, metabolic stress, and psychiatric disorders. The concentration of research productivity within certain countries and the limited extent of international collaboration indicate a need for more balanced global development in this field. Overall, the potential of fQRST as an accessible and low-cost biomarker in clinical practice is becoming increasingly evident, and the integration of large-scale, prospective, multicenter studies and AI-

driven analytical methods represents a key direction for future research.

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